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HYPERSPECTRAL IMAGE COMPRESSION USING CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS WITH LOCAL SPECTRAL TRANSFORMS AND NON-UNIFORM SAMPLE NORMALISATION

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ABSTRACT

In recent years there has been increasing interest in the usage of neural networks for image compression, with learned codecs achieving highly competitive results in comparison to conventional methods. Inspired by the success of these methods for natural images, a variety of designs and techniques have been proposed for neural compression of remote sensing data [1,2,3] and hyperspectral images [4,5,6].

A key challenge when compressing hyperspectral images in a band-by-band compression framework is that the distribution of samples may vary significantly from one channel to another, despite neighbouring channels being highly similar in general [7]. A learned codec trained to compress all channels in the image must, therefore, be able to adapt its transform to achieve high-performance results. We find transposed deconvolution -the standard operation in convolutional neural networks- produces significant artefacts in decompressing low-variance images, whose negative impact increases in proportion to the bit depth of the samples. To solve these issues, we propose the usage of non-uniform sample normalisation in neural network codecs for compression of hyperspectral images.

Much of the correlation among the samples of hyperspectral images is along the spectral axis. However, a spectral-spatial transform of a hyperspectral image (such as KLT+JPEG 2000) is computationally costly. To take advantage of local correlation among the channels without incurring into too high computational cost, our proposed learned transform performs local spectral-spatial decorrelation by compressing the image in batches of channels. In this paper we show that this is an effective solution for the artefacts we described and that our resulting neural-network codecs surpass current onboard payload data compression standards such as CCSDS 122.0, JPEG 2000, or KLT+JPEG 2000 in rate-distortion by up to 3dB PSNR. Finally, we discuss how this highly competitive method could be used in on-board settings and tradeoffs involved in that deployment.

INTRODUCTION

The use of Machine Learning (ML) of image compression has in recent years gone from a novelty application of neural networks to becoming the state-of-the-art image compression. Interest in research on the use of ML for natural image compression is growing, with proposed methods by now surpassing all state- of-the-art conventional codecs [8,9,10,11,12,13]. Successes in this field have pushed research in the deployment of similar ML codecs for remote sensing [1,2,3,14] and multispectral [4,15,16,17,18] images. In all fields of image compression, the designs by Ballé *et al.* [8,10] have served as a baseline architecture from which more sophisticated designs are developed.

In the field of remote sensing data compression there are two main established lossy compression standards for single-band images coding: JPEG 2000 [19] and the reduced-complexity standard CCSDS 122.0 [20]. On the other hand, for hyperspectral data, spectral-spatial decorrelation using the Karhunen-Loève Transform (KLT) for spectral decorrelation in combination with a Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) for spatial decorrelation (such as the earlier-mentioned CCSDS 122.0) is in widespread use as well and is shown to achieve nearly optimal results for a linear transform [21,22,23]. Therefore, in this contribution CCSDS 122.0 and KLT+JPEG 2000, serve as a reference to beat for onboard coding of hyperspectral remote sensing images.

A crucial factor in the development of onboard satellite imagery compression methods is computational cost. This is a major issue in the development of remote sensing data compression algorithms using ML, as these are, in general, much more costly to run than conventional methods such as JPEG or JPEG 2000 [1]. A variety of reduced-complexity neural-network compression methods have been proposed recently, of which we highlight the work by Alves de Oliveira *et al.* for single-band images [1,24], whom proposed a convolutional neural network (CNN) codec that surpassed JPEG 2000 while reducing computational cost to an acceptable level for modern hardware, and which inspired many aspects of our design.

Restrictions in computational cost also apply to conventional codecs, which imposes important limitations in the compression of multispectral and hyperspectral images. The aforementioned KLT is not used for onboard compression of hyperspectral images due to its high computational cost with an increasing number of bands. However, hyperspectral images have very high spectral correlation [7], which codecs may exploit to achieve much higher performance than when restricted to the spatial domain. As an intermediate point between band-by-band compression and full spectral decorrelation we propose to compress hyperspectral images in clusters of k channels at a time, which allows for some spectral decorrelation without incurring into too high computational cost.

Our proposed method uses a neural spectral linear transform (analogous to KLT) followed by a reduced-complexity convolutional neural network that compresses the output of that spectral transform band by band (analogous to how JPEG 2000 or CCSDS 122.0 are used in combination with KLT). In this paper we show that our method (1) is competitive with KLT+JPEG 2000 in compression of AVIRIS images in clusters of 4 bands at a time.

RELATED WORK

As argued by Ballé *et al.* [11], a key advantage of neural networks in image coding is the fact they can produce a non-linear transform, as opposed to conventional linear transforms used such as DWT or KLT. Alves de Oliveira *et al.* showed in [1] that a reduced-complexity version of the 2018 Ballé *et al.* hyperprior architecture [10] applied band-by-band coding remote sensing images surpasses JPEG 2000 for lossy compression, while bringing down computational cost to an acceptable level for modern hardware. Later Alves de Oliveira *et al.* proposed an extension of that earlier work for simultaneous compression and denoising of single-band remote sensing images [24].

Other works on successful ML compression of single-band remote sensing images include those by Xu *et al.* [25] and by Di *et al.* [26], both of which also use architectures based on the 2018 Ballé *et al.* hyperprior architecture. Authors Dua *et al.* published in 2021 a convolutional neural network (CNN)-based codec for AVIRIS images [6], whose results we have not been able to replicate. Authors Kong *et al.* [4], on the other hand, proposed an architecture for neural-network compression of multispectral remote sensing images (Landsat 8 and World-View 3), which successfully surpassed 3D-SPIHT and JPEG 2000 in lossy compression. Said architecture is, in our opinion, not suitable for compression of hyperspectral data, as the much larger number of channels in the input images makes that design far too computationally expensive for practical purposes. Following these precedents, we investigate the use of ML methods for hyperspectral data compression.

As explained in the introduction, computational cost is a major issue in the development of remote sensing data compression algorithms using ML. Besides the work by Alves de Oliveira *et al.* we cited earlier, other reduced-complexity ML methods have been proposed for remote sensing data compression: Mirrashid and Beheshti [2] proposed in 2018 a compressed sensing framework which made the encoder into a simple linear transform followed by a deep neural decoder. This system did not achieve highly competitive results with conventional codecs in lossy compression. Mirrashid and Shirazi [3] proposed in 2021 a second version of the earlier scheme, where the linear encoder transform was implemented as a convolution. Their performance results were highly competitive with other neural compressed sensing schemes, but no comparison was provided with common lossy compression standards such as JPEG, JPEG 2000 or CCSDS 122.0.

METHODOLOGY

In this section we will present what the architecture of our proposed ML method is, and compare the complexity of our algorithm with that of other similar neural-network codecs as well as conventional systems.

Fig. 1. Our proposed architecture. Blocks labeled $Conv N \times k \times k / s$ indicate $k \times k$ convolutions with N filters and a stride length of s (if $s \neq 1$), while the white arrows indicate downsampling or upsampling. Green blocks are activation functions, where GDN indicates General Divisive Normalisation, and $iGDN$ indicates Inverse General Divisive Normalisation [30], while $ReLU$ is a Rectified Linear Unit and abs indicates absolute value. $Quantisation$ is performed by rounding to the nearest integer. The yellow block indicates range-adaptive normalisation, where Max and Min are the maximum and minimum values of each channel. In our implementation, the number of bands is $B = 4$, the number of spectral filters is $F = 4$, the number of hidden spatial filters is $N = 64$ and the number of latent spatial filters is $M = 192$ or $M = 320$.

Table 1. Calculation of complexity of our models in number of parameters and FLOP/sample in each convolution and GDN layer, in order of calculation.

Layer name	Input filters	Output filters	Kernel size	Stride	Parameters	FLOP/sample
Norm	1	1	1	1	0	4
Conv (1D)	4	4	1	1	16	16
GDN (1D)	4	4		1	20	20
Conv	1	64	5	2	1.600	400
GDN	64	64		1	4.160	1.040
Conv	64	64	5	2	102.400	6.400
GDN	64	64		1	4.160	260
Conv	64	64	5	2	102.400	1.600
GDN	64	64		1	4.160	65
Conv	64	192	5	2	307.200	1.200
HConv	192	192	3	1	331.776	1.296
HConv	192	192	5	2	921.600	900
THConv	192	192	5	2	921.600	3.600
THConv	192	192	3	1	331.776	1.296
TConv	192	64	5	2	307.200	4.800
iGDN	64	64		1	4.160	65
TConv	64	64	5	2	102.400	6.400
iGDN	64	64		1	4.160	260
TConv	64	64	5	2	102.400	25.600
iGDN	64	64		1	4.160	1.040
TConv	64	1	5	2	1.600	1.600
iGDN (1D)	4	4		1	20	20
TConv (1D)	4	4	5	2	400	1.600
iNorm	4	4	1	1	0	4
Total					3.559.368	59.486
Encoder					3.032.868	18.097

Proposed Method

As described in the introduction, we propose to compress hyperspectral images in clusters of k channels at a time as an intermediate point between band-by-band compression and full spectral decorrelation, which allows for some spectral decorrelation without incurring into too high computational cost.

To illustrate why this scheme reduces computational cost, consider a linear transform (such as KLT) that maps n -dimensional vectors to n -dimensional vectors, $\Phi : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, and a second linear transform that maps k -dimensional vectors to k -dimensional vectors, $\Psi : \mathbb{R}^k \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^k$, which we apply in blocs of length in our n -dimensional vectors. Then, the calculation of the first one requires $O(n^2)$ operations (product by an $n \times n$ matrix), while the second one requires $O(\frac{n}{k}k^2) = O(nk)$ operations. Clearly, the smaller the blocks the quicker the operation, though this comes at the cost of a less refined transform (spectrally).

Our neural-network architecture is based on the use of convolutional autoencoders with a hyperprior for image compression framework proposed by Ballé *et al.* in 2018 [10], and the reduced-complexity version proposed by Alves de Oliveira *et al.* [1]. The later method was shown to be competitive in compression of single-band remote sensing

images with JPEG 2000 and CCSDS 122.0. Given those results, we propose an extension of that architecture analogous to the concatenation of KLT and CCSDS 122.0 for multispectral images. Our architecture, illustrated in Fig. 1, first performs a learned linear spectral transform on the samples (dark blue block), and then the output bands of said transform are coded one by one using an architecture analogous to that by Alves de Oliveira *et al.* [1] with a learned hyperprior.

ML architectures normalise the input samples to the $[0, 1]$ range¹ by dividing by the maximum possible value (i.e. 255 for 8-bit data, 65.535 for 16-bit unsigned integers, etc.). While 8-bit images typically use values all across the range, it is common for 16-bit images, particularly remote sensing images, to have their samples within a tight range relative to the overall possible range. We find that convolutional autoencoders will tend to produce checkerboard artefacts, especially in low-variance data, similar to those described by Odena, Dumoulin, and Olah [29]. Our proposed alternative is *range-adaptive normalisation* in each band: if Min_k and Max_k are the minimum and maximum sample values in the k band respectively, then we normalise the samples in each band as

$$X'_{k,j,i} = \frac{X_{k,j,i} - Min_k}{Max_k - Min_k + 1}$$

and store Min_k and Max_k as side information needed to reverse the range-adaptive normalisation process. In the denominator 1 is added for the special case of $Max_k = Min_k$.

Complexity Analysis

The simplified baseline proposed by Alves de Oliveira *et al.* that our method is based on encodes images using $\sim 1.25 \times 10^4$ FLOP per sample. Our network uses one fewer layer in the learned hyperprior, allowing our method, including the spectral transform, to be 2% less complex than the previous one, needing $\sim 1.8 \times 10^4$ FLOP per sample in the case of using 192 filters in the latent layer (Table 1), and needing $\sim 3.1 \times 10^4$ FLOP per sample if we expand that to 320 filters in the latent layer (analogous calculation to that of Table 1) for higher rates. This compares to the 140 operations per sample, or 70 multiplication accumulation (MAC) that CCSDS 122.0 performs, and the 2-3 more operations (depending on optimisations) needed by JPEG 2000 [1]. The calculation of KLT for 4-band images requires 22 more operations per sample, and the calculation of KLT for the full 224-channel spectrum requires 452 more operations per sample [31], bringing the total number of operations up by 15% and 323% respectively. In all our proposed method requires at least 40x more operations than KLT+JPEG 2000 applied in batches of 4 bands, and at least 20x more operations than KLT+JPEG 2000 applied to the whole spectrum.

Another complexity reference would be the usage of the Ballé *et al.* architecture [10] on said 4-band images. Performing a calculation analogous to that described in Table 1, and considering 192 filters in each layer of the encoder and decoder, the overall network would perform $\sim 9.6 \times 10^4$ FLOP per sample, meaning our design is more than 5 times less complex than the baseline, performing 18.75% of the operations of that codec.

Despite the higher number of operations required, our proposed method is not incompatible with current advanced hardware. As noted by Alves de Oliveira *et al.*, commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) components or dedicated hardware accelerators, based on a thinner silicon technology node, allow for higher processing frequencies with consistently lower consumption. For instance, the Movidius Myriad 2 announces 1 TFLOP/s/W. The 10 kFLOP/pixels of the current network would lead to 100 Mpixels/s/W on this component, hence the order of magnitude of the proposed method complexity is not incompatible with an embedded implementation, taking into account the technological leap from the component point of view [1]. The Google-developed TPU accelerators such as Coral, on the other hand, accelerate 10x the runtime of models like ours, and can perform 2TFLOP/W [32]. These technological leaps in hardware open the possibility of using more complex compression systems, such as that we propose in this paper, while keeping runtime competitive with present standards and improving compression performance.

EXPERIMENTS

Data Set

We conducted our experiments on calibrated data from the *Airborne Visible/Infrared Imaging Spectrometer* (AVIRIS) from a variety of sites across North America, 180 scenes for training and 20 scenes for testing [27]. The AVIRIS is an optical sensor that delivers images of the upwelling spectral radiance in 224 channels with wavelengths from 400 to 2.500 nanometers [28].

¹ Deep neural networks generally operate inputs in the $[0,1]$ or $[-1,1]$ ranges to avoid issues such as gradient explosion.
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Fig. 2. PSNR rate-distortion performance of our proposed method and other codecs on the AVIRIS test set.

Fig. 3. PSNR rate-distortion performance of the Ballé *et al.* 2018 architecture and KLT+JPEG 2000 applied in batches of 3 channels on AVIRIS images.

For the training of our models, we preprocessed every scene in our training set by partitioning it into 56 clusters of 4 bands. This way our models were trained on the exact clusters of 4 channels they would later be compressing, as opposed to having training samples from any 4 consecutive bands in the images.

Compression Performance

We trained 4 models with 192 filters (for lower rates) and 4 models with 320 filters (for higher rates) using the setup described in Fig. 1 on the AVIRIS data set described above, and then tested those models on the aforementioned test set in batches of 4 channels at a time. We tested KLT+JPEG 2000 on said batches of 4 channels at a time as well, as opposed to applying KLT along the entire spectrum of AVIRIS images, as well as JPEG 2000 and CCSDS 122.0.

Fig. 2 depicts the rate-distortion of our models and KLT+JPEG 2000 applied to AVIRIS images in 4-band clusters, as well as JPEG 2000 and CCSDS-122.0 applied band by band and KLT+JPEG 2000 applied on the whole 224-band spectrum. Our 192-filter models surpassed KLT+JPEG 2000 by up to 3.6dB (at 0.28bps), though at higher rates (0.7bps) they fell below KLT+JPEG 2000. Our models with 320 filters in the latent layer performed similarly to the 192-filter versions, though were more successful at higher rates, surpassing KLT+JPEG 2000 at rates up to 0.75bps.

While our codecs match and even surpass KLT+JPEG 2000 in compression, the reduction in complexity does lower their performance with respect to the usage of the Ballé *et al.* baseline architecture in batches of bands. Fig. 3 shows the capabilities of the non-simplified Ballé *et al.* 2018 baseline architecture as well as KLT+JPEG 2000 on 3-band clusters of AVIRIS images. Said architecture can outperform KLT+JPEG 2000 in compression of AVIRIS images in clusters of 3 bands by up to 7dB at similar rates to our proposed models (0.32bps). As noted in an earlier section, this comes at close to 8 times more computational cost, an increase likely unassumable in an on board scenario.

Visual Comparison

In Fig. 4 we may compare visually the reconstructions at 0.1576bps of one of the bands in our test AVIRIS images by our 192-filter models and KLT+JPEG 2000 applied in clusters of 4 bands or across the entire 224-channel spectrum. Fig. 5 shows a close-up of a portion of the images in Fig. 4. Especially from Fig. 5 we can see how our models produced images with smoother features than KLT+JPEG 2000 applied in 4-band clusters, where we can see some dot-like artifacts in compression. In any case, it is clear that KLT+JPEG 2000 applied on the whole spectrum produced a higher-quality reconstruction in this case. At higher rates -0.5bps and higher, achieving 68dB PSNR and above- no significant differences can be appreciated visually among the three reconstructions and the original, even as the numerical performance differences remain.

Fig. 4. Visualisation of a section of band 40 from the scene f080806t01p00r07 decompressed using one of our 192-filter models, and KLT+JPEG 2000 applied in 4-band clusters on on the whole 224-band spectrum.

Fig. 5. Visualisation of a zoom-in of band 40 from the scene f080806t01p00r07 decompressed using one of our 192-filter models, and KLT+JPEG 2000 applied in 4-band clusters on on the whole 224-band spectrum.

CONCLUSION

In this paper we have presented a reduced-complexity method for compression of hyperspectral images, applying a learned 1D+2D transform in clusters of 4 channels at a time. Our experimental results show our proposed method is competitive with remote sensing data compression standards such as KLT+JPEG 2000 applied in a similar fashion. While other ML image codecs would be more more competitive than our proposal in rate-distortion, those would come at a far higher computational cost.

Despite the significant complexity reduction in our method compared to the baseline ML architecture, it remains significantly more complex than KLT+JPEG 2000. Nevertheless, advances in onboard payload hardware capabilities and the rise in usage of COTS components mean the deployment of a codec such as our proposal is computationally feasible, while other existing architectures probably wouldn't be so in any near future.

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